

slightly higher locations (medium high to medium low lands).

6. Farmers normally used low or even no potassic fertilizers during the last few years.

7. Rice is cultivated continuously in almost all three seasons in some places. Usually only Paiam, the susceptible var-

ety, is used for three consecutive seasons.

In addition to the above factors, the development of new virulent races of the highly variable causal fungus *Pyricularia oryzae* and the immigration to Bangladesh of spores of races different from those already present are also possible.

Thus, the identification of the new races and of the number of races existing in Bangladesh and efforts to find chemical control measures are immediate steps being taken in the research programs of the BRRI Pathology Division. Studies on the interaction of ufra and blast have also been undertaken. ■

Varietal and insecticidal trial against rice tungro virus

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A trial with 10 test cultivars, which aimed at determining the effect of insecticidal treatment on the control of the vector insect of rice tungro virus (RTV), was laid out in split plots with 3 replications during 1979 thaladi. The treatments were: root soaking with FMC 35001 24% EC at 0.04% along with 1% urea for 20 minutes, maximum protection in which carbofuran 3% G was applied at 0.5 kg a.i./ha 10, 25, and 45 days after transplanting (DT); and an untreated control.

ADT 32 and AD 7211 had low percentages of RTV while ADT 31 and AD 9105 had high percentages (see table).

Data on rice tungro virus (RTV) incidence from an insecticidal trial, Tamil Nadu, India, 1979 thaladi.

Variety	RTV incidence (%)			Mean
	Root soaking	Max protection	Control	
AD 10969	56.0	52.3	52.0	53.4
AD 7211	25.3	22.0	27.7	25.0
TKM 9	39.3	35.3	41.7	38.8
AD 6120	62.7	63.7	60.7	62.4
AD 12599	68.7	58.7	67.3	64.9
ADT 32	33.3	10.3	22.3	22.0
ASD 15	42.7	14.3	46.0	34.3
IR20	56.3	16.3	45.3	39.3
ADT 31	92.3	93.0	100.0	95.1
AD 9105	97.7	92.7	100.0	96.8
Mean	57.4	45.9	56.3	

C.D. (P = 0.05%)	Insecticidal treatment	Varieties	Interaction
	2.3	5.4	3.2

In seven varieties – ADT 31, AD 9105, AD 6120, AD 12599, AD 10969, TKM 9 and AD 7211 – insecticidal treatment did not appreciably reduce RTV incidence by controlling the vector

insects.

In IR20, ASD15, and ADT32, maximum protection gave good reduction of RTV. ■

Outbreak of glume discoloration in Haryana, India

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Grain spotting, also known as glume discoloration (GLD) or dirty panicle, appears sporadically each crop season in Haryana on Basmati 370 and late-emerging panicles of IR8 and Jaya. Seventy-two percent discolored grains was recorded on RP967-4-1-10 and 31.5% in Basmati 370 in the 1978 wet season. Of the mycoflora associated with harvested grains, *Trichoconis padwickii* (in 60-80% discolored grains) was predominant over *Curvularia lunata*, *Drechslera oryzae*, *Phoma* sp., *Fusarium*

semitectum, *F. moniliforme*, and *Pyricularia oryzae*.

A glume discoloration outbreak occurred in September 1979, after a long drought followed by rainfall and a storm when the crop was in the panicle-emergence stage. All emerging panicles

had dirty brown or black grains. Symptoms appeared before the milk stage, and caused farmers to fear that they would not even get seed for their next crop. Pollen grains were viable, but no one could predict if grains would form. High sterility of spikelets and their

Occurrence of glume discoloration (GLD) under natural conditions at the Kaul Rice Research Station, India, in 1979 kharif.

Score	GLD (%)	No.	Cultivars showing discoloration	
			%	Designation
1	<1	110	38	Improved Sona, PAU1-608A, Sabarmati, R36-2486
3	1-5	58	20	Pusa 2-21, Prasad
5	5-25	35	12	Palman 579, Sona, Badshah Pasand
7	25-50	37	13	Basmati 370, IR36, PR106
9	>50	60	20	Ratna, Jaya, RP967-4-7-4, RP967-4-1-10, RP967-11-4-22

dirty color led to prediction of heavy losses, but the spikelets later filled. The table shows GLD incidence on various cultivars.

Isolations on PDA from affected glumes and grains showed *C. lunata* (in

80% discolored grains) and *F. semitectum* (5%). Unlike in the 1978 wet season, *C. lunata* was prominent.

Inoculating *C. lunata* on emerged panicles by spraying and dipping, and on the boot stage by injecting spore or

mycelial suspensions on three dates produced symptoms of dirty panicle on almost all glumes and grains. *F. semitectum* did not produce discoloration by any of the tested inoculation procedures. ■

Survival of sclerotia of *Corticium sasakii* at different soil depths

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Sclerotia of *Corticium sasakii* (Shirai) Matsumoto — the rice sheath blight fungus — were grown on sterilized rice grain for 1½ months and then placed in a layer of 5, 10, and 15 cm deep soil respectively, in clay pots. On 17 August 1978, the pots were buried in a highland where the level of the soil of the pot and that of the field were the same. The soil in the pot contained 0.336% organic

carbon, 0.09% N, 57.3 kg available P₂O₅/ha, 1,111.5 kg available K₂O/ha and pH 6.95. The sclerotia with the soil mass from the different depths were taken out at monthly intervals, starting

Viability of sclerotia of *C. sasakii* buried at different soil depths (observation from 15 sclerotia), Assam, India.

Observation time (mo after start of study)	Viability of sclerotia (%) at soil depth of		
	5 cm	10cm	15 cm
3	1	1	2
4	1	1	1
6	1	1	2
7	2	2	2
8	1	2	1

at 3 months of burial, and retrieved by washing over a mesh. These were then surface-sterilized with mercuric chloride and viability was tested by growing them on potato dextrose agar mixed with streptomycin sulfate.

The table shows that the viability of sclerotia dropped considerably after 3 months (first observation) and remained almost the same, regardless of the depth of burial, up to 8 months (last observation). Sclerotia from the different soil depths were found to be colonized by different organisms including *Trichoderma viride*, but those retrieved from below 5 cm were colonized most and those from below 15 cm least. ■

Effect of seed treatment with fungicides in improving germination of sheath rot-infected seeds

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Sheath rot disease of rice caused by *Sarocladium attenuatum* Gams and Hawkworth caused grain discoloration of seeds in varieties ADT31, Bhavani, CO39, and CO40. In all four varieties, 45% of seeds died before emergence and seedlings that survived were about 30% (Table 1).

Six fungicides were tested for their efficiency in the control of seed germination failure. For each treatment 50 g seeds showing infection symptoms was

Table 1. Data on germination^a of 4 varieties, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Pre-emergence death (no.)	Post-emergence death (no.)	Seedlings that survived (no.)
ADT31	45	24	31
Bhavani	42	26	32
CO39	45	30	25
CO40	41	29	30

^aMean of 3 replications.

Table 2. Effect of fungicide seed treatment on germination. Tamil Nadu, India.

Fungicide	Germination ^a (%)	
	Immediately after seed treatment	After 6 mo storage
TMTD	60 (51)	47 (43)
Captan	72 (58)	56 (48)
Agrosan	66 (54)	52 (46)
Panoctine	75 (60)	67 (55)
Panoram	55 (48)	43 (41)
Benomyl	82 (65)	76 (61)
Control	44 (42)	24 (30)
SED	4.06	2.38
CD (P = 0.05)	8.72	(P = 0.05) 5.11

^aMean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are transformed values.

treated with fungicides at 2 g or 2 ml/kg seed. The seeds were then sown in pots containing 2 kg sterilized wetland soil. Untreated infected seeds were sown as the control. Another set of seeds treated with fungicides was stored in the laboratory at 25± 1°C for 6 months, then tested for germination 10 days after sowing.

Benomyl and panoctine improved seed germination best, both immediately after the treatment and after 6 months storage (Table 2). ■

Influence of diammonium phosphate on brown spot disease of rice

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Brown spot of rice caused by *Helminthosporium oryzae* is very severe at the seedling stage during *navarai* (Nov-Mar) and *thaladi* (Oct-Feb) seasons. A field experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with four replications during 1979 *navarai*. IR20, which is susceptible to brown leaf spot disease, was raised in a 5- x 2-m plot. Diammonium phosphate (DAP) was applied to the nursery and disease incidence was observed. The treatments were: 1) wet seed treatment with DAP at 0.5% for 10 hours; 2) sprouted seed treatment with DAP at 0.5% for 30 minutes; 3) basal dressing of 500 g DAP/10 m²; 4) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 7th day; 5) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the 15th day; 6) foliar spraying with 0.5% DAP on the 7th day; 7) foliar spraying with 0.5% DAP on the 15th day; 8) topdressing of 500 g DAP/10 m² on the